

Prevalence and Determinants of Age-Related Macular Degeneration in the 50 Years and Older PopulationPoonam¹, Pinki Kumari², Gyan Bhaskar³¹Senior Resident, Regional Institute of Ophthalmology, IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Regional Institute of Ophthalmology, IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India³Professor, Regional Institute of Ophthalmology, IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India

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Abstract:**Background:** As the world's population ages, age-related macular degeneration, or AMD, is predicted to become more common among older persons and cause visual impairment. Appropriate prevention and management efforts for AMD require an understanding of the disease's incidence and determinants.**Aim:** This study aimed to assess the prevalence of AMD and identify its key determinants among adults aged 50 years and older in Patna, Bihar.**Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted. A total of 107 participants aged 50 years and older were recruited. Data were collected through structured interviews and comprehensive eye examinations, including fundus photography. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with logistic regression used to identify determinants of AMD.**Results:** The prevalence of AMD in the study population was 26.2%, with 16.8% of participants having early AMD and 9.3% having late AMD. Age and current smoking were significant determinants of AMD, with the risk increasing with age (OR 1.08 per year) and smoking (OR 2.15). Other factors, including gender, BMI, hypertension, and diabetes, were not significantly associated with AMD.**Conclusion:** The study highlights a high prevalence of AMD among older adults in Patna, with age and smoking identified as significant risk factors. These findings underscore the need for targeted public health interventions focusing on smoking cessation and regular eye screenings for early detection.**Recommendations:** Public health programs should prioritize smoking cessation campaigns and implement regular eye examination protocols for older adults. Further research is needed to explore other potential determinants of AMD and to develop comprehensive prevention strategies.**Keywords:** Age-Related Macular Degeneration, Prevalence, Determinants, Smoking, Elderly Population.

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Introduction

AMD is one of the primary factors contributing to visual loss and blindness in the elderly. With rising life expectancy and an ageing population, there will likely be a large increase in the global burden of AMD [1]. The macula, the core region of the retina. It offers sharp, precise vision, is the main target of AMD, a degenerative retinal disease. In more advanced phases, the development of geographic atrophy or choroidal neovascularisation, which result in significant vision loss, is characterised by pigmentary alterations and drusen accumulation in the retinal pigment epithelium [2].

Due to a variety of factors, including age, genetics, lifestyle, and environmental exposures, the prevalence of AMD differs greatly between various populations [3]. According to a new meta-analysis, there were about 196 million AMD sufferers globally in 2020, and by 2040, there are expected to be 288 million [4]. AMD is a serious issue for

the general population since it causes 8.7% of all incidents of blindness in high-income nations [5]. The primary risk factor for AMD is age that has been found. Beyond the age of 50, the chance of having AMD increases dramatically, with the predominance doubling every ten years [6]. A significant influence is also played by genetic predisposition; mutations in the age-related maculopathy susceptibility 2 and complement factor H genes are substantially linked to an elevated risk of AMD [7]. The risk is further modulated by environmental factors as nutrition, smoking, and UV light exposure. Since smoking increases inflammation and oxidative stress, two factors crucial to AMD pathogenesis, it has been repeatedly demonstrated that smoking doubles the risk of the illness [8].

Managing AMD is still difficult, especially when the illness is advanced. The therapy of neovascular

AMD anti-vascular endothelial growth factor (anti-VEGF) drugs have changed; yet, the disease is still incurable and response to treatment differs [9]. Maintaining vision and halting the spread of AMD to an advanced stage requires early detection and treatments. An important part of managing AMD is identifying modifiable risk factors, like quitting smoking and making dietary changes, and doing routine eye exams [10]. This study aimed to assess the prevalence of AMD and identify its key determinants among adults aged 50 years and older in Patna, Bihar.

Methodology

Study Design: This study employed a cross-sectional design.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences (IGIMS), Patna, a tertiary care hospital that serves a large population in the region. The Ophthalmology Department at IGIMS provided the clinical setting for the recruitment and examination of participants. The study was conducted over a period of 11 months, from August 2019 to June 2020.

Participants: A total of 107 participants aged 50 years and older were included in the study. These participants were recruited from patients attending the Ophthalmology Department at IGIMS for routine eye check-ups or other ophthalmic issues.

Inclusion Criteria

- Individuals aged 50 years and older.
- Participants who provided informed consent to participate in the study.
- Patients with no prior diagnosis of AMD at the time of recruitment.

Exclusion Criteria

- Individuals younger than 50 years of age.
- Patients with any form of secondary macular degeneration not related to age.
- Participants with significant ocular comorbidities, such as diabetic retinopathy or glaucoma, that could confound the diagnosis of AMD.

- Patients with cognitive impairments or other conditions that might hinder their ability to provide informed consent or cooperate with the examination.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible patients who met the inclusion criteria and attended the Ophthalmology Department during the study period were invited to participate. Observer bias was reduced by training all clinical staff involved in the assessment of AMD to follow standardized protocols. The analysis accounted for potential confounders to minimize bias in the interpretation of results.

Data Collection: Data were collected through direct patient interviews and clinical examinations. A structured questionnaire was used to gather demographic information, medical history, and lifestyle factors, such as smoking and diet, which could be associated with AMD. Clinical data, including visual acuity, fundus examination findings, and the presence of drusen or other signs of AMD, were recorded for each participant.

Procedure: Each participant underwent a comprehensive eye examination, including visual acuity testing and fundus photography. Fundus examination was performed using an ophthalmoscope or a fundus camera to identify the presence and stage of AMD. The collected data were documented in a standardized form.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic and clinical characteristics. AMD prevalence was calculated, and logistic regression identified determinants, with significant associations reported as odds ratios (ORs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs). A p-value of <0.05 was deemed statistically significant.

Results

A total of 107 participants aged 50 years and older were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 65.3 ± 8.2 years, with a range of 50 to 85 years. The study population consisted of 56 males (52.3%) and 51 females (47.7%).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Participants (n=107)

Characteristic	Frequency (%)
Age Group (years)	
50-59	30 (28.0)
60-69	42 (39.3)
70-79	25 (23.4)
≥80	10 (9.3)
Gender	
Male	56 (52.3)
Female	51 (47.7)
Smoking Status	
Current Smoker	20 (18.7)

Former Smoker	32 (29.9)
Never Smoked	55 (51.4)
Body Mass Index (BMI)	
<18.5 (Underweight)	5 (4.7)
18.5-24.9 (Normal weight)	62 (57.9)
25-29.9 (Overweight)	30 (28.0)
≥30 (Obese)	10 (9.3)
Hypertension	
Yes	45 (42.1)
No	62 (57.9)
Diabetes Mellitus	
Yes	22 (20.6)
No	85 (79.4)

Prevalence of (AMD): The overall predominance of AMD in the study population was found to be 26.2% (28 out of 107 participants). Among these, 18 participants (16.8%) had early AMD, and 10 participants (9.3%) had late AMD, including 4

cases of geographic atrophy and 6 cases of neovascular AMD.

The predominance of AMD increased with age, from 16.7% in the 50-59 age group to 50% in the ≥80 age group ($p < 0.01$). Table 2 presents the prevalence of AMD across different age groups.

Table 2: Prevalence of AMD by Age Group

Age Group (years)	Number of Participants	Prevalence of AMD (%)	Early AMD (%)	Late AMD (%)
50-59	30	5 (16.7)	3 (10.0)	2 (6.7)
60-69	42	9 (21.4)	6 (14.3)	3 (7.1)
70-79	25	8 (32.0)	5 (20.0)	3 (12.0)
≥80	10	5 (50.0)	4 (40.0)	1 (10.0)
Total	107	28 (26.2)	18 (16.8)	10 (9.3)

Determinants of AMD: Logistic regression analysis was conducted to identify potential determinants of AMD, including age, gender, smoking status, BMI, hypertension, and diabetes mellitus. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Logistic Regression Analysis of Determinants of AMD

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Age (per year increase)	1.08	1.03-1.15	0.002**
Male Gender	1.25	0.75-2.10	0.39
Current Smoker	2.15	1.05-4.38	0.037**
Former Smoker	1.60	0.85-3.00	0.14
BMI ≥ 25 (Overweight/Obese)	1.32	0.70-2.50	0.39
Hypertension	1.75	0.92-3.32	0.08
Diabetes Mellitus	1.58	0.74-3.40	0.24

Significant at $p < 0.05$

The analysis revealed that age (OR 1.08; 95% CI 1.03-1.15; $p=0.002$) and current smoking (OR 2.15; 95% CI 1.05-4.38; $p=0.037$) were significant determinants of AMD. Other factors, including gender, BMI, hypertension, and diabetes, were not statistically significant in this study.

Discussion

According to the study, 26.2% of participants 50 years of age and older had Alzheimer's disease. This suggests that AMD affects more than 25% of the older population in the research area. Given the potential effects of AMD on vision and quality of life, AMD is a serious public health concern. With 16.8% of individuals exhibiting early-stage disease

symptoms compared to 9.3% with late-stage AMD cases, which included both geographic atrophy and neovascular AMD, early AMD was more common than late AMD.

One important factor that determined AMD in this investigation was age. AMD was significantly more common as people aged, rising from 16.7% in the 50–59 age group to 50% in the 80+ age group. This result is in line with previous research that indicates an increased risk of AMD with ageing, especially in those over 60. In order to manage and potentially halt the progression of the illness, regular eye exams and early detection techniques are crucial for older populations, as seen by the

strong correlation between age and AMD (OR 1.08 per year).

Smoking was identified as another significant determinant of AMD. Current smokers had more than double the risk of developing AMD compared to non-smokers (OR 2.15). This finding aligns with previous research that links smoking to oxidative stress and vascular changes in the retina, both of which have a role in AMD's aetiology. Although the residual risk may last for some time after cessation, stopping smoking may lower the risk of getting AMD, according to the lack of a statistically significant link with former smokers.

Interestingly, other factors such as gender, BMI, hypertension, and diabetes mellitus did not show a statistically significant association with AMD in this study. While these factors have been implicated in some studies, their role in AMD may be more complex and influenced by interactions with other risk factors, such as genetic predisposition and lifestyle behaviors. The lack of significance in this study could also be due to the relatively small sample size or the specific characteristics of the study population.

A systematic review and meta-analysis focussing on the European population found that AMD is a major cause of vision impairment and blindness in that region. According to the study, there are already 67 million AMD sufferers in the European Union, and as the population ages, this figure is predicted to increase. According to Li et al. (2019), the predominance of early or intermediate AMD was determined to be 25.3%, while the predominance of late-stage AMD was 2.4% in those 60 years of age and older [11].

A population-based study conducted in Russia evaluated AMD prevalence in both rural and urban areas. According to the study, AMD prevalence is higher in Russia than in East Asia but lower in Western Europe. Older age, living in a rural area, important AMD variables included a decreased prevalence of diabetes mellitus and a shorter axial length. These findings, according to Bikbov et al. (2019), emphasise the importance of regional and demographic factors in the prevalence of AMD [12].

Over a 4-year period, another significant study from France that was a component of the ALIENOR cohort recorded the incidence of and risk variables related to AMD. The study discovered that certain genetic markers (e.g., CFH Y402H genotype) and a greater grade of AMD in the companion eye were substantially related with the progression from early to advanced AMD. Significant incidence rates of both early and severe AMD highlight the necessity for high-risk individuals to have monitoring and preventative measures in place [13].

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Conclusion

The study's findings emphasise the strong influence of age and smoking on the risk of developing AMD among older adults. These findings suggest the need for targeted public health interventions, including smoking cessation programs and age-specific screening protocols, to decrease the impact of AMD and shield this susceptible group's sight.

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